

A Rapid Field Method for the Detection and Determination of Formaldehyde releasing Pollutants

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Formaldehyde is one of the major industrial chemicals contained in ambient air. Looking into its toxicity and importance as the major industrial pollutant, a large number of colorimetric methods have been developed¹.

It has been found that formaldehyde reacts with phloroglucinol and sodium hydroxide to give orange-red coloured compound with maximum absorbance at ~470 nm. This reagent system has been used here to prepare indicator tubes and reagent papers.

Results and Discussion

Constant and maximum absorbance values were obtained taking 0.05 M phloroglucinol and 1.45 M NaOH in 3 : 1 ratio. A 1.5% KMnO₄ in 15% H₃PO₄ was found to be optimum as it gave maximum colour intensity and good stability. A 2 ml of oxidising solution was found to be sufficient for complete oxidation. Few mg of magnesium powder in 0.5 ml of 2 N HCl was found to be sufficient for reduction of formic acid. At extremely dry conditions the colour development did not occur. Small amount of humidity was always necessary and 0.5 ml of 5% CaCl₂ was sufficient to maintain it.

The lower limit of detection (per drop) of the formaldehyde released from various pollutants and pesticides were found to be : methanol (0.0075 µg); 2,4-D (0.175 µg); 2,4,5-T (0.25 µg); phorate (0.125 µg); formaldehyde (0.0012 µg); ethylene glycol (0.125 µg); ethion (0.05 µg) and formic acid (0.025 µg).

In comparison to other reported indicator tube methods the proposed method is rapid, selective and highly sensitive for the detection and semiquantitative determination of formaldehyde and formaldehyde precursors including some well-known pesticides.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade or the best quality available. Double-distilled deionised water was used.

A Carl-Zeiss spekol with 1 cm matched silica cells was used. 35 ml midiget impingers and PIMCO calibrated rotameters were used for indicator tubes.

The following stock solutions (1 mg ml⁻¹ each) were used in different solvents : aqueous methanol (Loba),

aqueous 2,4-D (B.D.H.), 2,4,5-T (Fluka) in acetone, aqueous formaldehyde (ExcelaR), phorate (NECL, India) in chloroform, ethion (Shaw Wallace) in acetone, aqueous ethylene glycol (H.P.C.) and aqueous formic acid (B.D.H.). Working standards were prepared by appropriate dilution.

A 5% CaCl₂ (0.5 ml) was added with stirring to a mixture of 0.05 M phloroglucinol and 1.45 M NaOH in 3 : 1 ratio and the reagent was used for the preparation of indicator tubes and reagent papers.

A 1.5% KMnO₄ in 15% H₃PO₄ was used as oxidising solution and 2 N HCl (0.5 ml) with magnesium powder was used as reducing agent.

Preparation of indicator tube and paper : One end of the graduated glass tube (6 × 0.5 cm i.d.) was plugged with glass-wool (~2 cm). Then the cellulose fibre impregnated with the reagent solution and dried filled to another 2 cm length. The other end of the tube was filled with glass wool. The sealed tube (stable upto 1 month) were then kept in a dessiccator. The test paper (Whatman no. 1, strip 4 × 2 cm) was prepared by dipping it in a reagent solution and dried in a thermostat (40°) for 30 min. The test paper was stable upto ~1 month when kept in air-tight bottle.

Procedure : To a mixture of known amount of the sample with oxidising solution (2 ml) and known amount of formic acid taken in a test tube were added few mg of Mg powder and 2 N HCl (0.5 ml). Methanol, phorate, ethion, formic acid released formaldehyde at ~100° while 2,4-D and 2,4,5-T released formaldehyde at ~135° which was detected and determined by the orange-red colour developed in the reagent papers and indicator tubes.

Procedure with indicator tube : The sealed ends of the indicator tubes were cut prior to the estimation of formaldehyde released from the pollutants and pesticides. One end of the indicator tube was connected to the rotameter and the other end to the 35 ml midiget impinger containing known amount of pollutant with oxidising solution except formic acid which was treated with reducing solution. The flow-rate was controlled with a calibrated rotameter and maintained at 1 dm³ min⁻¹. The formaldehyde released at a particular temperature was passed through the tube and indicated by the orange-red colour stain developed on the cellulose fiber. The coloured substance was extracted in water (5 ml) and the absorbance measured at ~470 nm.

Procedure with test paper : The known amount of respective pollutants were taken in a test tube with oxidising solution (2 ml) except formic acid which was treated with the reducing solution to release formaldehyde. Test paper was kept at the mouth of the test tube. On heating the test tubes (the temperature maintained as required for a concerned pollutant) the orange-red colour developed on the test paper indicated the release of formaldehyde.

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References

1. D. E. KRAMM and C. L. KOLBE, *Anal. Chem.*, 1975, **27**, 1076; C. W. LEE, Y. S. FUNG and K. W. FUNG, *Analyst*, 1982, **107**, 30; M. TANENBAUM and C. E. BRICKER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, **23**, 354; E. SAWICKI and T. R. HAUSER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1960, **32**, 1434; E. SAWICKI, T. R. HAUSER and W. C. ELBERT, *Anal. Chem.*, 1961, **33**, 93; E. SAWICKI, T. R. HAUSER and S. MCPHERSON, *Anal. Chem.*, 1962, **34**, 1460; J. CHRASTIL and J. T. WILSON, *Anal. Bio. Chem.*, 1975, **63**, 202; J. R. MUDEKAVI and M. RAVINDRAM, *Curr. Sci.*, 1982, **51**, 39; M. S. A. LATTIF and G. GUILBAULT, *Anal. Lett.*, 1989, **2**, 1955; A. GOLD, D. F. UTTERBACK and D. S. MILLINGTON, *Anal. Chem.*, 1984, **56**, 2879.
2. V. FEDOTOV, *Zh. Khim.*, 1957, 310